

Obtainment of Mueller-Jones matrix from output Stokes vectors

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Abstract

The Jones matrix, and hence the Mueller-Jones matrix can be characterized by seven real parameters: one real and three complex parameters. In principle, any Mueller matrix can be obtained from six output Stokes vectors. If the Mueller matrix of a deterministic optical system has a symmetry then only two output Stokes vectors is enough to determine the remaining five real parameters. If, in addition to the symmetry, all nonzero complex parameters are real or pure imaginary then just a single output Stokes vector is enough. This note intends to demonstrate the internal consistency of the theorem that was recently put forward. The theorem states that there exists a relation between the outer product of input-output Stokes vectors and outer product of complex vectors. Complex vectors are obtained as a result of transformation of Stokes vectors by \mathbf{Z} matrices. \mathbf{Z} matrices are 4×4 analogues of Jones matrices. It is shown that determination of all relevant parameters that characterize a deterministic optical system can also be accomplished by means of the theorem. It is also discussed that complex parameters can be altered by a rotation about the z -axis, and it is shown that in some cases it is possible to make one complex parameter zero by simply rotating the optical system.

1 Introduction

If the optical system is deterministic its optical properties can be represented by a Jones matrix, and alternatively, by a vector state $|h\rangle$ or by a matrix state \mathbf{Z} [1]. Components of the vector state can be parametrized as τ , α , β and γ :

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where τ , α , β and γ are generally complex numbers. For convenience, it can be assumed that $|h\rangle$ is normalized, i.e., $\langle h|h\rangle = \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* = 1$. If the overall phase is

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not taken into account one of the parameters, for example τ , can be chosen to be real and positive. In that case, the number of independent real parameters will be seven. It was shown that α , β and γ can be associated with complex anisotropy parameters of the optical system [1]. In terms of spectroscopic parameters, isotropic phase retardation (η), isotropic amplitude absorption (κ), circular dichroism (CD), circular birefringence (CB), horizontal and 45° linear dichroism (LD and LD'), horizontal and 45° linear birefringence (LB and LB'), τ , α , β and γ can be written as:

$$\tau = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \alpha = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL'}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \gamma = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iC}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $\chi = \eta - i\kappa$, $L = LB - iLD$, $L' = LB' - iLD'$, $C = CB - iCD$, $T = \sqrt{L^2 + L'^2 + C^2}$.

Every $|h\rangle$ vector generates a nondepolarizing Mueller matrix according to the following scheme:

$$|h\rangle \longrightarrow \mathfrak{H} = |h\rangle\langle h| \longrightarrow \Sigma(\mathfrak{H}) = \mathbf{M}, \quad (4)$$

where Σ denotes a special transformation described in Appendix 1.

\mathbf{Z} matrix is another form of the vector state $|h\rangle$:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \beta & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

In terms of \mathbf{Z} matrices Mueller matrix of a deterministic optical system can be written as,

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z}. \quad (6)$$

Eq.(6) leads to an expression for the Mueller-Jones matrix in terms of τ, α, β and γ :

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* & \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* & \tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^* \\ \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* & +i(\gamma\beta^* - \beta\gamma^*) & +i(\alpha\gamma^* - \gamma\alpha^*) & +i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* & \alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^* & \alpha\gamma^* + \gamma\alpha^* \\ -i(\gamma\beta^* - \beta\gamma^*) & -\beta\beta^* - \gamma\gamma^* & +i(\tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^*) & +i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* & \alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^* & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* & \beta\gamma^* + \gamma\beta^* \\ -i(\alpha\gamma^* - \gamma\alpha^*) & -i(\tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^*) & +\beta\beta^* - \gamma\gamma^* & +i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ \tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^* & \alpha\gamma^* + \gamma\alpha^* & \beta\gamma^* + \gamma\beta^* & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* \\ -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) & -i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) & -i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) & -\beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Some properties of nondepolarizing Mueller matrices can be immediately obtained from Eq.(7). It can be shown that $tr(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{M}^T) = 4M_{00}^2$. It is also possible to show that $M_{01}^2 + M_{02}^2 + M_{03}^2 = M_{10}^2 + M_{20}^2 + M_{30}^2$.

\mathbf{Z} matrix is a 4×4 analogue of the Jones matrix, \mathbf{J} [3]:

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \alpha & \beta - i\gamma \\ \beta + i\gamma & \tau - \alpha \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Jones matrices transform two component Jones vectors, $|E\rangle$, into Jones vectors, $|E'\rangle$, and Mueller matrices transform four component Stokes vectors, $|s\rangle$, into Stokes vectors, $|s'\rangle$:

$$|E'\rangle = \mathbf{J}|E\rangle; \quad |s'\rangle = \mathbf{M}|s\rangle, \quad (9)$$

where $|s\rangle = (s_0, s_1, s_2, s_3)^T$, $|s'\rangle = (s'_0, s'_1, s'_2, s'_3)^T$ (s_i and s'_i are real numbers). If the Mueller matrix is nondepolarizing and if $|s\rangle$ represents completely polarized light then $|s'\rangle$ is also completely polarized.

\mathbf{Z} matrix transforms the Stokes matrix \mathbf{S} into a Stokes matrix \mathbf{S}' according to the following scheme:

$$\mathbf{S}' = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{Z}^\dagger \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{Z}^\dagger is the Hermitian conjugate of \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{S} is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} s_0 & s_1 & s_2 & s_3 \\ s_1 & s_0 & -is_3 & s_2 \\ s_2 & is_3 & s_0 & -is_1 \\ s_3 & -is_2 & is_1 & s_0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

\mathbf{S}' matrix has a similar form, but matrix elements interchanged with components of transformed Stokes vector, $|s'\rangle$.

\mathbf{Z} matrix also transforms the Stokes vector of completely polarized light, $|s\rangle$, into a $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector:

$$|\tilde{s}\rangle = \mathbf{Z}|s\rangle, \quad (12)$$

where $|\tilde{s}\rangle = (\tilde{s}_0, \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \tilde{s}_3)^T$ and $\tilde{s}_0, \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2$ and \tilde{s}_3 are, in general, complex numbers. It can be shown that, just like the Jones matrix, \mathbf{Z} matrix and hence $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector bears the total phase introduced by the optical system [3]:

$$\langle E|E'\rangle = \langle E|\mathbf{J}|E\rangle = \frac{1}{2}\langle s|\mathbf{Z}|s\rangle = \frac{1}{2}\langle s|\tilde{s}\rangle. \quad (13)$$

2 Obtainment of Mueller-Jones matrix from output Stokes vectors

Mueller-Jones matrix of a deterministic optical system can be obtained from the Jones matrix:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{J} \otimes \mathbf{J}^*)\mathbf{U}^\dagger, \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{U}^\dagger is a unitary matrix given in Appendix 1. The Jones matrix, and hence the Mueller-Jones matrix can be characterized by seven real parameters: one real parameter for τ and six real parameters for complex parameters, α, β and γ . If the Mueller-Jones matrix of the optical system is known, all seven parameters can be obtained from the Mueller-Jones matrix by the Σ transformation [5].

Mueller matrix of an optical is a matrix with real valued elements. In principle, any Mueller matrix can be obtained from six output Stokes vectors. If the Mueller matrix of a deterministic optical system has a symmetry, i.e., if one of the complex parameters (α, β or

γ) is zero then only two output Stokes vectors is enough to determine the remaining five real parameters. If, in addition to the symmetry, all nonzero parameters are pure real or pure imaginary (except τ) then just a single output Stokes vector is enough.

Suppose that a set of output Stokes vectors ($|s'\rangle$) associated with a set of input Stokes vectors ($|s\rangle$) are known. In principle, it is possible to obtain 16 elements of any Mueller matrix from six output Stokes vectors associated with the following input Stokes vectors:

$$|s_1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, |s_2\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, |s_3\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |s_4\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |s_5\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |s_6\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

For example, from two output Stokes vectors associated with inputs $|s_1\rangle$ and $|s_2\rangle$ the first and the last columns of the Mueller matrix can be obtained.

Now, consider the case with a Mueller matrix symmetry. For example let $\gamma = 0$, Mueller matrix given by Eq.(7) reduces to the following form:

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* & \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* & i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* - \beta\beta^* & \alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^* & i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* & \alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^* & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* & i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) & -i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) & -i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* - \beta\beta^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Consider the action of this Mueller matrix on the input Stokes vectors, $|s_1\rangle$ and $|s_2\rangle$:

$$\mathbf{M}|s_1\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* + i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* + i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) + \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* - \beta\beta^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} s'_{10} \\ s'_{11} \\ s'_{12} \\ s'_{13} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{M}|s_2\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* - i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* - i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* - i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) - \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} s'_{20} \\ s'_{21} \\ s'_{22} \\ s'_{23} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

where $|s'_i\rangle = (s'_{i0}, s'_{i1}, s'_{i2}, s'_{i3})^T$ is the output Stokes vector that corresponds to the input Stokes vector, $|s_i\rangle$. It can be shown that from Eqs.(17) and (18) it is possible to find all nonzero parameters. For example, assuming that τ is real

$$s'_{10} + s'_{13} = \tau\tau^* \longrightarrow \tau = \sqrt{s'_{10} + s'_{13}}. \quad (19)$$

Once the value of τ is determined it is easy to find real and imaginary parts of the complex parameters from Eqs.(17) and (18).

If, in addition to the symmetry, all nonzero parameters are pure real or pure imaginary then only a single Stokes vector measurement will be enough to determine the Mueller-Jones matrix. For example, if $\gamma = 0$ and all parameters are real valued then they can be calculated

from Eq.(17). For $\gamma = 0$, Eq.(17) reduces to a simple relation:

$$\mathbf{M}|s_1\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau^2 + \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \\ 2\tau\alpha \\ 2\tau\beta \\ \tau^2 - \alpha^2 - \beta^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} s'_{10} \\ s'_{11} \\ s'_{12} \\ s'_{13} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

Hence,

$$\tau = \sqrt{s'_{10} + s'_{13}}, \quad \alpha = \frac{s'_{11}}{\tau}, \quad \beta = \frac{s'_{12}}{\tau}. \quad (21)$$

In short, all parameters of a Mueller-Jones matrix can be obtained from output Stokes vectors. But, the aim of this note is to show the internal consistency of the recently introduced calculus for polarization optics that is based on the \mathbf{Z} matrix formulation of the Stokes-Mueller formalism [1].

3 Theorem on the outer product of input and output Stokes vectors

Recently it was shown that there exists a relation between input-output Stokes vectors and $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vectors [4]. The relation can be formulated between real \mathbf{K} and complex \mathfrak{S} matrices defined by the following outer products:

$$\mathbf{K} = |s'\rangle\langle s|, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathfrak{S} = |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle\tilde{s}|. \quad (23)$$

\mathbf{K} matrix has the following explicit form:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} s'_0 s_0 & s'_0 s_1 & s'_0 s_2 & s'_0 s_3 \\ s'_1 s_0 & s'_1 s_1 & s'_1 s_2 & s'_1 s_3 \\ s'_2 s_0 & s'_2 s_1 & s'_2 s_2 & s'_2 s_3 \\ s'_3 s_0 & s'_3 s_1 & s'_3 s_2 & s'_3 s_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

where $|s\rangle$ and $|s'\rangle$ represent complete polarization. \mathfrak{S} is a complex-Hermitian matrix with the following explicit form:

$$\mathfrak{S} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{s}_0 \tilde{s}_0^* & \tilde{s}_0 \tilde{s}_1^* & \tilde{s}_0 \tilde{s}_2^* & \tilde{s}_0 \tilde{s}_3^* \\ \tilde{s}_1 \tilde{s}_0^* & \tilde{s}_1 \tilde{s}_1^* & \tilde{s}_1 \tilde{s}_2^* & \tilde{s}_1 \tilde{s}_3^* \\ \tilde{s}_2 \tilde{s}_0^* & \tilde{s}_2 \tilde{s}_1^* & \tilde{s}_2 \tilde{s}_2^* & \tilde{s}_2 \tilde{s}_3^* \\ \tilde{s}_3 \tilde{s}_0^* & \tilde{s}_3 \tilde{s}_1^* & \tilde{s}_3 \tilde{s}_2^* & \tilde{s}_3 \tilde{s}_3^* \end{pmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

\mathbf{K} and \mathfrak{S} matrices can be bridged by a Σ transformation (Appendix 1):

$$\mathfrak{S} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 K_{ij} \Sigma_{ij}, \quad (26)$$

where K_{ij} are the elements of \mathbf{K} matrix and Σ_{ij} are basis matrices. Explicit form of \mathfrak{S} matrix in terms of elements of \mathbf{K} matrix can be obtained from the following transformation table:

$$\mathfrak{S} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} K_{00} + K_{11} & K_{01} + K_{10} & K_{02} + K_{20} & K_{03} + K_{30} \\ K_{22} + K_{33} & -i(K_{23} - K_{32}) & +i(K_{13} - K_{31}) & -i(K_{12} - K_{21}) \\ K_{01} + K_{10} & K_{00} + K_{11} & K_{12} + K_{21} & K_{13} + K_{31} \\ +i(K_{23} - K_{32}) & -K_{22} - K_{33} & +i(K_{03} - K_{30}) & -i(K_{02} - K_{20}) \\ K_{02} + K_{20} & K_{12} + K_{21} & K_{00} - K_{11} & K_{23} + K_{32} \\ -i(K_{13} - K_{31}) & -i(K_{03} - K_{30}) & +K_{22} - K_{33} & +i(K_{01} - K_{10}) \\ K_{03} + K_{30} & K_{13} + K_{31} & K_{23} + K_{32} & K_{00} - K_{11} \\ +i(K_{12} - K_{21}) & +i(K_{02} - K_{20}) & -i(K_{01} - K_{10}) & -K_{22} + K_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

It is worth noting that $\text{rank}(\mathfrak{S}) = 1$, hence, all column vectors of \mathfrak{S} matrix are equivalent to each other, i.e., column vectors differ from each other only by respective phases. Column vectors are also equivalent to $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector apart from overall phase factors.

4 Obtainment of Mueller-Jones matrix from the outer products of input and output Stokes vectors

In principle, it is possible to obtain the Mueller matrix from six output Stokes vectors, and τ, α, β and γ can be found by the Σ transformation as described in Section 2. But, this note intends to make use of the theorem. Suppose that the Mueller matrix \mathbf{M} is not given, instead, $|s\rangle$ and $|s'\rangle$ vectors are known, then $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector can be calculated from the outer product, $|s'\rangle\langle s|$, and this procedure can be used to find τ, α, β and γ .

In general, six output Stokes vectors associated with the input Stokes vectors that given by (15) are needed. Let $|s'_i\rangle = (s'_{i0}, s'_{i1}, s'_{i2}, s'_{i3})^T$ be the output Stokes vector that corresponds to the input Stokes vector, $|s_i\rangle$. $\mathbf{K}_i = |s'_i\rangle\langle s_i|$ matrix can be calculated, and after the Σ transformation it is possible to make the connection with $|\tilde{s}_i\rangle$ vector:

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_i) = \mathfrak{S}_i = |\tilde{s}_i\rangle\langle\tilde{s}_i|, \quad (28)$$

where $|\tilde{s}_i\rangle = \mathbf{Z}|s_i\rangle$. For example,

$$|\tilde{s}_1\rangle = \mathbf{Z}|s_1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \gamma \\ \alpha + i\beta \\ \beta - i\alpha \\ \gamma + \tau \end{pmatrix}, \quad (29)$$

$$|\tilde{s}_1\rangle\langle\tilde{s}_1| = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \gamma \\ \alpha + i\beta \\ \beta - i\alpha \\ \gamma + \tau \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* + \gamma^*, \quad \alpha^* - i\beta^*, \quad \beta^* + i\alpha^*, \quad \gamma^* + \tau^*). \quad (30)$$

Fist columns of all $\mathfrak{S}_i = |\tilde{s}_i\rangle\langle\tilde{s}_i|$ matrices can be written as follows:

$$\mathfrak{S}_1 \longrightarrow \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \gamma \\ \alpha + i\beta \\ \beta - i\alpha \\ \gamma + \tau \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* + \gamma^*), \quad \mathfrak{S}_2 \longrightarrow \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau - \gamma \\ \alpha - i\beta \\ \beta + i\alpha \\ \gamma - \tau \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* - \gamma^*), \quad (31)$$

$$\mathfrak{S}_3 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \beta \\ \alpha - i\gamma \\ \beta + \tau \\ \gamma + i\alpha \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* + \beta^*), \quad \mathfrak{S}_4 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau - \beta \\ \alpha + i\gamma \\ \beta - \tau \\ \gamma - i\alpha \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* - \beta^*), \quad (32)$$

$$\mathfrak{S}_5 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \alpha \\ \alpha + \tau \\ \beta + i\gamma \\ \gamma - i\beta \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* + \alpha^*), \quad \mathfrak{S}_6 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau - \alpha \\ \alpha - \tau \\ \beta - i\gamma \\ \gamma + i\beta \end{pmatrix} (\tau^* - \alpha^*). \quad (33)$$

Eq.(28) and Eqs.(31)-(33) yield 12 equations:

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tau\tau^* + \tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^* + \gamma\gamma^*) = Q_1 \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha\tau^* + \alpha\gamma^* + i\beta\tau^* + i\beta\gamma^*) = Q_2 \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tau\tau^* - \tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^* + \gamma\gamma^*) = Q_3 \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha\tau^* - \alpha\gamma^* - i\beta\tau^* + i\beta\gamma^*) = Q_4 \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tau\tau^* + \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* + \beta\beta^*) = Q_5 \quad (38)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha\tau^* + \alpha\beta^* - i\gamma\tau^* - i\gamma\beta^*) = Q_6 \quad (39)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tau\tau^* - \tau\beta^* - \beta\tau^* + \beta\beta^*) = Q_7 \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha\tau^* - \alpha\beta^* + i\gamma\tau^* - i\gamma\beta^*) = Q_8 \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tau\tau^* + \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^*) = Q_9 \quad (42)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\beta\tau^* + \beta\alpha^* + i\gamma\tau^* + i\gamma\alpha^*) = Q_{10} \quad (43)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tau\tau^* - \tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^*) = Q_{11} \quad (44)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\beta\tau^* - \beta\alpha^* - i\gamma\tau^* + i\gamma\alpha^*) = Q_{12} \quad (45)$$

where Q_j is the associated component of the first column of $\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_i)$ matrix.

τ, α, β and γ can be calculated from Eqs.(34)-(45). For example, real part of γ can be calculated in terms of τ from Eq.(34) and Eq.(36):

$$\tau(\gamma + \gamma^*) = (Q_1 - Q_3), \quad (46)$$

where it is assumed that τ is real and positive. Real parts of α and β can be found in similar ways.

Imaginary parts of complex parameters also can be found. For example, in order to find the imaginary part of α Eq.(35) is added to Eq.(37) and Eq.(39) is added to Eq.(41):

$$\alpha\tau + i\beta\gamma^* = (Q_2 + Q_4), \quad (47)$$

$$\alpha\tau - i\gamma\beta^* = (Q_6 + Q_8). \quad (48)$$

Imaginary part of α is obtained in terms of τ as follows:

$$\tau(\alpha - \alpha^*) = (Q_2 + Q_4) - (Q_6 + Q_8)^*. \quad (49)$$

Similarly, imaginary parts of β and γ can be found in terms of τ . Finally, τ is found by adding Eqs.(34), (36), (38), (40), (42) and (44):

$$3\tau^2 + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* = Q_1 + Q_3 + Q_5 + Q_7 + Q_9 + Q_{11}. \quad (50)$$

For convenience, it is assumed that $|h\rangle$ vector is normalized to unity, hence, $\tau^2 + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* = 1$,

$$2\tau^2 = (Q_1 + Q_3 + Q_5 + Q_7 + Q_9 + Q_{11}) - 1. \quad (51)$$

As a result, τ and all other parameters can be solved completely. Note that, once τ, α, β and γ are found, the Mueller-Jones matrix of the optical system can be immediately obtained by the relation $\mathbf{ZZ}^* = \mathbf{M}$. A worked example is given in Appendix 2.

In Eqs.(50) and (51) normalization condition of $|h\rangle$ is used. This condition is not necessary. In general, $|h\rangle$ may not be normalized to unity. But, it is always possible to recover the value of $\langle h|h\rangle$ from output Stokes vectors. It can be observed that

$$s'_{10} + s'_{20} = s'_{30} + s'_{40} = s'_{50} + s'_{60} = 2M_{00} = \langle h|h\rangle = \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^*, \quad (52)$$

and this relation allows to work with unnormalized $|h\rangle$ vectors. Real and positive τ assumption can also be relaxed. A worked example for unnormalized $|h\rangle$ and complex τ is also given in Appendix 2.

If one of the parameters α, β , or γ is equal to zero, then it is possible to find the remaining parameters from two output Stokes vectors. For example, if $\gamma = 0$, two output Stokes vectors associated with input stokes vectors $|s_1\rangle$ and $|s_2\rangle$ are enough. In this case, Eq.(34), Eq.(35) and Eq.(37) can be written as

$$\frac{1}{2}\tau\tau^* = Q_1, \quad (53)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha\tau^* + i\beta\tau^*) = Q_2, \quad (54)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\alpha\tau^* - i\beta\tau^*) = Q_4. \quad (55)$$

From Eqs.(53)-(55) τ , α and β can be solved by assuming that τ is real and positive. Similar considerations apply to the case $\alpha = 0$ with input Stokes vectors $|s_5\rangle$ and $|s_6\rangle$, and to the case $\beta = 0$ with input Stokes vectors $|s_3\rangle$ and $|s_4\rangle$.

Anisotropy parameters depend on the orientation of the optical system. It can be shown that, if the optical system is rotated by an angle θ about the z axis τ and γ are not affected by the rotation, but α and β get mixed. Symmetries of the $|h\rangle$ vector and effect of the rotation on the symmetries is discussed in Appendix 3, and it is shown that in some cases it is possible to make either α or β equal to zero by simply rotating the optical system.

If, in addition to the symmetry property, all nonzero parameters are real numbers, they can be found from a single output Stokes vector. For example, for $\gamma = 0$ with an input Stokes vector $|s_1\rangle$, Eq.(34) and Eq.(35) give,

$$\frac{\tau^2}{2} = Q_1, \quad (56)$$

$$\frac{\tau}{2}(\alpha + i\beta) = Q_2. \quad (57)$$

From Eq.(56), $\tau = \sqrt{2Q_1}$, and from Eq.(57) α and β can be directly read from the real and imaginary parts of $2Q_2/\tau$. A system state with real parameters corresponds to a pure diattenuator.

If all parameters (except τ) are pure imaginary the optical system is a pure retarder. In this case also, if there is a symmetry, all nonzero parameters can be found from a single output Stokes vector. For example, if $\gamma = 0$ and if α and β are pure imaginary all nonzero parameters can be solved from Eqs.(56) and (57) in a similar way. Accordingly, if α or β is zero ($\gamma \neq 0$), an output Stokes vector associated with an input $|s_5\rangle$ or $|s_3\rangle$ can be used, respectively, to find nonzero parameters of a pure diattenuator or a pure retarder.

5 Conclusion

The Jones matrix, and hence the Mueller-Jones matrix can be characterized by seven real parameters: one real and three complex parameters. In principle, any Mueller matrix can be obtained from six output Stokes vectors. If the Mueller matrix of a deterministic optical system has a symmetry then only two output Stokes vectors are enough to determine the remaining five real parameters. If, in addition to the symmetry, all nonzero parameters are real or pure imaginary (except τ) then just a single output Stokes vector is enough.

This note intends to demonstrate the internal consistency of the theorem that was recently put forward. The theorem states that there exists a relation between input-output Stokes vectors and complex vectors. Complex vectors are obtained as a result of transformation of Stokes vectors by \mathbf{Z} matrices. \mathbf{Z} matrices are 4×4 analogues of Jones matrices. It is shown that determination of all relevant parameters that characterize a deterministic optical system can also be accomplished by means of the theorem.

Previously, it was shown that \mathbf{Z} matrix is a 4×4 analogue of the Jones matrix and \mathbf{Z} matrix transforms the Stokes vector $|s\rangle$ into a complex vector $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ ($|\tilde{s}\rangle = \mathbf{Z}|s\rangle$). A real matrix \mathbf{K} is defined as an outer product of input and output Stokes vectors, $\mathbf{K} = |s'\rangle\langle s|$. A Hermitian matrix can be obtained from \mathbf{K} matrix by the Σ transformation, and according

to the theorem, $\Sigma(\mathbf{K}) = |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle\tilde{s}|$. By means of the theorem $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector can be calculated from the outer product of $|s\rangle$ and $|s'\rangle$ vectors. In this note several applications of this theorem are studied and it is shown that, in general, all parameters of deterministic optical systems can be obtained from six output Stokes vectors. The method becomes more efficient as the number of parameters decreases. If the system has a symmetry, i.e., if one of the complex parameters (α, β or γ) is zero then only two output Stokes vectors are enough to determine nonzero parameters. In addition to the symmetry property, if the optical system is a pure diattenuator or a pure retarder, all nonzero parameters can be found by a single output Stokes vector. It is also discussed that $|h\rangle$ vector associated with the rotated optical system is more suitable to investigate the effect of rotation of the optical system on the anisotropy parameters, and it is shown that in some cases it is possible to make one complex parameter zero by simply rotating the optical system about the z axis.

6 Appendix 1

A Hermitian matrix \mathfrak{H} can be associated with a real matrix \mathbf{M} according to the following transformation:

$$\mathfrak{H} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 M_{ij} \Sigma_{ij}, \quad (58)$$

where M_{ij} ($i, j = 0, 1, 2, 3$) are the elements of the real matrix \mathbf{M} and $\Sigma_{ij} = \mathbf{U}(\sigma_i \otimes \sigma_j^*)\mathbf{U}^{-1}$ with,

$$\mathbf{U} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U}^{-1} = \mathbf{U}^\dagger = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & i \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (59)$$

The superscript \dagger indicates the complex conjugate and transpose, the superscript $*$ indicates complex conjugate, \otimes is the Kronecker product and σ_i are the Pauli matrices with the 2×2 identity in the following order:

$$\sigma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (60)$$

The transformation given by Eq.(58) can be denoted by a symbol Σ :

$$\mathfrak{H} = \Sigma(\mathbf{M}). \quad (61)$$

Σ is the inverse of its own, it also transforms \mathfrak{H} into \mathbf{M} :

$$\mathbf{M} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{H}). \quad (62)$$

7 Appendix 2

Let $\tau = 1/3$, $\alpha = 2i/3$, $\beta = (1+i)/3$ and $\gamma = (1-i)/3$:

$$|h\rangle = \frac{1}{3} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2i \\ 1+i \\ 1-i \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Z} = \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2i & 1+i & 1-i \\ 2i & 1 & -1-i & -1+i \\ 1+i & 1+i & 1 & 2 \\ 1-i & 1-i & -2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 9 & 4 & -2 & 6 \\ -4 & 1 & 2 & -6 \\ 6 & 6 & -3 & 4 \\ -2 & -2 & -4 & -3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (63)$$

Suppose that input and output Stokes vectors were calculated from $|s'_i\rangle = \mathbf{M}|s_i\rangle$:

$$|s_1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_1\rangle = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 15 \\ -10 \\ 10 \\ -5 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |s_2\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_2\rangle = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 3 \\ 2 \\ 2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (64)$$

$$|s_3\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_3\rangle = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 7 \\ -2 \\ 3 \\ -6 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |s_4\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_4\rangle = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 11 \\ -6 \\ 9 \\ 2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (65)$$

$$|s_5\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_5\rangle = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 13 \\ -3 \\ 12 \\ -4 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |s_6\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_6\rangle = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ -5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (66)$$

Associated $\mathbf{K}_i = |s'_i\rangle\langle s_i|$ matrices:

$$\mathbf{K}_1 = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 15 & 0 & 0 & 15 \\ -10 & 0 & 0 & -10 \\ 10 & 0 & 0 & 10 \\ -5 & 0 & 0 & -5 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_2 = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 & 0 & -3 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & -2 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & -2 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (67)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_3 = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 0 & 7 & 0 \\ -2 & 0 & -2 & 0 \\ 3 & 0 & 3 & 0 \\ -6 & 0 & -6 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_4 = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 11 & 0 & -11 & 0 \\ -6 & 0 & 6 & 0 \\ 9 & 0 & -9 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & -2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (68)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_5 = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 13 & 13 & 0 & 0 \\ -3 & -3 & 0 & 0 \\ 12 & 12 & 0 & 0 \\ -4 & -4 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_6 = \frac{1}{18} \begin{pmatrix} 5 & -5 & 0 & 0 \\ -5 & 5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (69)$$

Transformed \mathbf{K}_i matrices:

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_1) = \frac{1}{36} \begin{pmatrix} 10 & -10-10i & 10-10i & 10 \\ -10+10i & 20 & 20i & -10+10i \\ 10+10i & -20i & 20 & 10+10i \\ 10 & -10-10i & 10-10i & 10 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma(\mathbf{K}_2) = \frac{1}{36} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 2+2i & 2-2i & -2 \\ 2-2i & 4 & -4i & -2+2i \\ 2+2i & 4i & 4 & -2-2i \\ -2 & -2-2i & -2+2i & 2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (70)$$

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_3) = \frac{1}{36} \begin{pmatrix} 10 & -2-6i & 10 & -6+2i \\ -2+6i & 4 & -2+6i & -4i \\ 10 & -2-6i & 10 & -6+2i \\ -6-2i & 4i & -6-2i & 4 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma(\mathbf{K}_4) = \frac{1}{36} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -6-2i & -2 & 2-6i \\ -6+2i & 20 & 6-2i & 20i \\ -2 & 6+2i & 2 & -2+6i \\ 2+6i & -20i & -2-6i & 20 \end{pmatrix} \quad (71)$$

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_5) = \frac{1}{36} \begin{pmatrix} 10 & 10 & 12+4i & -4+12i \\ 10 & 10 & 12+4i & -4+12i \\ 12-4i & 12-4i & 16 & 16i \\ -4-12i & -4-12i & -16i & 16 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma(\mathbf{K}_6) = \frac{1}{36} \begin{pmatrix} 10 & -10 & 0 & 0 \\ -10 & 10 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (72)$$

According to the theorem \mathfrak{S}_i matrix is equal to \mathbf{K}_i matrix, hence, from the first columns of these matrices following equations can be written:

$$\tau\tau^* + \tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^* + \gamma\gamma^* = \frac{5}{9} \quad (73)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* + \alpha\gamma^* + i\beta\tau^* + i\beta\gamma^* = \frac{-5+5i}{9} \quad (74)$$

$$\tau\tau^* - \tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^* + \gamma\gamma^* = \frac{1}{9} \quad (75)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* - \alpha\gamma^* - i\beta\tau^* + i\beta\gamma^* = \frac{1-i}{9} \quad (76)$$

$$\tau\tau^* + \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* + \beta\beta^* = \frac{5}{9} \quad (77)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* + \alpha\beta^* - i\gamma\tau^* - i\gamma\beta^* = \frac{-1+3i}{9} \quad (78)$$

$$\tau\tau^* - \tau\beta^* - \beta\tau^* + \beta\beta^* = \frac{1}{9} \quad (79)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* - \alpha\beta^* + i\gamma\tau^* - i\gamma\beta^* = \frac{-3+i}{9} \quad (80)$$

$$\tau\tau^* + \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* = \frac{5}{9} \quad (81)$$

$$\beta\tau^* + \beta\alpha^* + i\gamma\tau^* + i\gamma\alpha^* = \frac{6-2i}{9} \quad (82)$$

$$\tau\tau^* - \tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* = \frac{5}{9} \quad (83)$$

$$\beta\tau^* - \beta\alpha^* - i\gamma\tau^* + i\gamma\alpha^* = 0 \quad (84)$$

From these equations it is possible to find τ, α, β and γ as described in Section 3. For example τ is found by adding Eqs.(73), (75), (77), (79), (81), (83):

$$6\tau\tau^* + 2\alpha\alpha^* + 2\beta\beta^* + 2\gamma\gamma^* = \frac{22}{9}. \quad (85)$$

Using the normalization of $|h\rangle$,

$$\tau\tau^* = \frac{1}{9}, \quad (86)$$

Hence $\tau = \frac{1}{3}$.

As a second example let $|h\rangle$ be an unnormalized vector with $\tau = 1+i, \alpha = 2-i, \beta = 4-2i$ and $\gamma = 2i$:

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1+i \\ 2-i \\ 4-2i \\ 2i \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Z} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1+i & 2-i & 4-2i & 2i \\ 2-i & 1+i & 2 & 2+4i \\ 4-2i & -2 & 1+i & -1-2i \\ 2i & -2-4i & 1+2i & 1+i \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 31 & -14 & 12 & 4 \\ 18 & -17 & 24 & 8 \\ -4 & 16 & 13 & -14 \\ 4 & -16 & -2 & -19 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (87)$$

Note that, in this example, τ is not chosen to be real and positive, but this is not important, it is possible to find the associated parameters apart from an overall phase.

Suppose that input and output Stokes vectors were calculated from $|s'_i\rangle = \mathbf{M}|s_i\rangle$:

$$|s_1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_1\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 35 \\ 26 \\ -18 \\ -15 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |s_2\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_2\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 27 \\ 10 \\ 10 \\ 23 \end{pmatrix} \quad (88)$$

$$|s_3\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_3\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 43 \\ 42 \\ 9 \\ 2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |s_4\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_4\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 19 \\ -6 \\ -17 \\ 6 \end{pmatrix} \quad (89)$$

$$|s_5\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_5\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 17 \\ 1 \\ 12 \\ -12 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |s_6\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow |s'_6\rangle = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 45 \\ 35 \\ -20 \\ 20 \end{pmatrix} \quad (90)$$

Associated $\mathbf{K}_i = |s'_i\rangle\langle s_i|$ matrices:

$$\mathbf{K}_1 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 35 & 0 & 0 & 35 \\ 26 & 0 & 0 & 26 \\ -18 & 0 & 0 & -18 \\ -15 & 0 & 0 & -15 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_2 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 27 & 0 & 0 & -27 \\ 10 & 0 & 0 & -10 \\ 10 & 0 & 0 & -10 \\ 23 & 0 & 0 & -23 \end{pmatrix} \quad (91)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_3 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 43 & 0 & 43 & 0 \\ 42 & 0 & 42 & 0 \\ 9 & 0 & 9 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_4 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 19 & 0 & -19 & 0 \\ -6 & 0 & 6 & 0 \\ -17 & 0 & 17 & 0 \\ 6 & 0 & -6 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (92)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_5 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 17 & 17 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 12 & 12 & 0 & 0 \\ -12 & -12 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_6 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 45 & -45 & 0 & 0 \\ 35 & -35 & 0 & 0 \\ -20 & 20 & 0 & 0 \\ 20 & -20 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (93)$$

First columns of transformed \mathbf{K}_i matrices:

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_1) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 20 \\ 26 - 18i \\ -18 - 26i \\ 20 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma(\mathbf{K}_2) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 4 \\ 10 - 10i \\ 10 + 10i \\ -4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (94)$$

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_3) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 52 \\ 42 - 2i \\ 52 \\ 2 + 42i \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma(\mathbf{K}_4) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 36 \\ -6 + 6i \\ -36 \\ 6 + 6i \end{pmatrix} \quad (95)$$

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{K}_5) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 18 \\ 18 \\ 12 - 12i \\ -12 - 12i \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Sigma(\mathbf{K}_6) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 10 \\ -10 \\ -20 - 20i \\ 20 - 20i \end{pmatrix} \quad (96)$$

According to the theorem \mathfrak{S}_i matrix is equal to \mathbf{K}_i matrix, hence, from the first columns of these matrices following equations can be written:

$$\tau\tau^* + \tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^* + \gamma\gamma^* = 10 \quad (97)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* + \alpha\gamma^* + i\beta\tau^* + i\beta\gamma^* = 13 - 9i \quad (98)$$

$$\tau\tau^* - \tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^* + \gamma\gamma^* = 2 \quad (99)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* - \alpha\gamma^* - i\beta\tau^* + i\beta\gamma^* = 5 - 5i \quad (100)$$

$$\tau\tau^* + \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* + \beta\beta^* = 26 \quad (101)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* + \alpha\beta^* - i\gamma\tau^* - i\gamma\beta^* = 21 - i \quad (102)$$

$$\tau\tau^* - \tau\beta^* - \beta\tau^* + \beta\beta^* = 18 \quad (103)$$

$$\alpha\tau^* - \alpha\beta^* + i\gamma\tau^* - i\gamma\beta^* = -3 + 3i \quad (104)$$

$$\tau\tau^* + \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* = 9 \quad (105)$$

$$\beta\tau^* + \beta\alpha^* + i\gamma\tau^* + i\gamma\alpha^* = 6 - 6i \quad (106)$$

$$\tau\tau^* - \tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* = 5 \quad (107)$$

$$\beta\tau^* - \beta\alpha^* - i\gamma\tau^* + i\gamma\alpha^* = -10 - 10i \quad (108)$$

To find τ add equations (97), (99), (101), (103), (105), (107):

$$6\tau\tau^* + 2\alpha\alpha^* + 2\beta\beta^* + 2\gamma\gamma^* = 70 \quad (109)$$

$s'_{10} + s'_{20} = 31$, therefore, $\tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* = 31$,

$$4\tau\tau^* = 8. \quad (110)$$

Assuming that the overall phase is discarded and τ can be taken as real and positive, $\tau = \sqrt{2}$, and α, β and γ are found as $\alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - 3i)$, $\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(2 - 6i)$, $\gamma = \sqrt{2}(1 + i)$. These results can be written in a vector form:

$$|\bar{h}\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{2} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - 3i) \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(2 - 6i) \\ \sqrt{2}(1 + i) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (111)$$

This vector is equivalent to the vector in Eq.(87):

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i \\ 2 - i \\ 4 - 2i \\ 2i \end{pmatrix} = \frac{(1 + i)}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{2} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - 3i) \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(2 - 6i) \\ \sqrt{2}(1 + i) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (112)$$

where $\frac{(1+i)}{\sqrt{2}}$ is just an overall phase.

8 Appendix 3

If the optical element is rotated by an angle θ about the z axis the Jones matrix transforms accordingly:

$$\mathbf{J}(\theta) = \mathbf{t}(\theta)\mathbf{J}\mathbf{t}(-\theta), \quad (113)$$

where $\mathbf{t}(\theta)$ is the rotation matrix, which is also a Jones matrix:

$$\mathbf{t}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (114)$$

Transformation of \mathbf{Z} matrix under a rotation is very similar to Eq.(113):

$$\mathbf{Z}(\theta) = \mathbf{T}(\theta)\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{T}(-\theta), \quad (115)$$

where $\mathbf{T}(\theta)$ is the rotation matrix, which is also a \mathbf{Z} matrix:

$$\mathbf{T}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & 0 & -i \sin \theta \\ 0 & \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ 0 & \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ -i \sin \theta & 0 & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (116)$$

$\mathbf{T}(\theta)$ matrix can be obtained from $\mathbf{t}(\theta)$ matrix:

$$\mathbf{T}(\theta) = \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{t}(\theta) \otimes \mathbf{I})\mathbf{U}^\dagger. \quad (117)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the 2×2 identity and \mathbf{U} is given by Eq.(59).

The Mueller matrix of the optical system is rotated by $\mathbf{R}(\theta)$ matrix:

$$\mathbf{M}(\theta) = \mathbf{R}(\theta)\mathbf{M}\mathbf{R}(-\theta), \quad (118)$$

where $\mathbf{R}(\theta)$ is the rotation matrix which is also a Mueller matrix:

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos 2\theta & -\sin 2\theta & 0 \\ 0 & \sin 2\theta & \cos 2\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (119)$$

$\mathbf{R}(\theta)$ matrix can be obtained from $\mathbf{T}(\theta)$ matrix:

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta) = \mathbf{T}(\theta)\mathbf{T}(\theta)^*. \quad (120)$$

Eqs.(113), (115) and (118) do not tell much about what happens to τ, α, β and γ parameters as a result of the rotation. It was shown elsewhere that there exists a rotation formula for $|h\rangle$ vector also [3]:

$$|h(\theta)\rangle = \mathbf{R}(\theta)|h\rangle. \quad (121)$$

$|h(\theta)\rangle$ vector generates the rotated nondepolarizing Mueller matrix, $\mathbf{M}(\theta)$, according to scheme given in Eq.(4):

$$|h(\theta)\rangle \longrightarrow \mathfrak{H}(\theta) = |h(\theta)\rangle\langle h(\theta)| \longrightarrow \Sigma(\mathfrak{H}(\theta)) = \mathbf{M}(\theta). \quad (122)$$

When Eq.(121) is written explicitly it can be easily seen what happens to τ, α, β and γ :

$$|h(\theta)\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \tau(\theta) \\ \alpha(\theta) \\ \beta(\theta) \\ \gamma(\theta) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \alpha \cos 2\theta - \beta \sin 2\theta \\ \alpha \sin 2\theta + \beta \cos 2\theta \\ \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (123)$$

First of all, τ and γ are not affected by the rotation about the z axis. Secondly, the norm of the $|h\rangle$ vector is preserved:

$$\langle h(\theta)|h(\theta)\rangle = \langle h|h\rangle. \quad (124)$$

Rotation about the z axis mixes only α and β parameters.

Since, $|h\rangle$ vectors are the generators of nondepolarizing Mueller matrices, Mueller matrix symmetries can be classified with respect to nonzero parameters of $|h\rangle$ vectors [1]. For example, if $\tau \neq 0, \alpha \neq 0, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0$, Mueller matrix can be written as

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* & \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & 0 & 0 \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* & i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ 0 & 0 & -i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (125)$$

where $M_{00} = M_{11}, M_{22} = M_{33}, M_{01} = M_{10}, M_{23} = -M_{32}$.

As it is shown in Section 2 and Section 4, if one of the parameters (α, β or γ) is zero, all nonzero parameters can be found from two output Stokes vectors. Rotation about the z axis does not alter τ and γ , but, if $\alpha = \lambda\beta$ (λ is a real number) it possible to rotate the optical system by an angle θ to make either α or β equal to zero. For example, a rotation with $\theta_1 = \frac{1}{2} \arctan(\lambda)$ makes $\alpha(\theta_1) = 0$; a rotation with $\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2} \arctan(-\frac{1}{\lambda})$ makes $\beta(\theta_2) = 0$.

As an example, consider the second example of Appendix 2, where $\tau = 1 + i, \alpha = 2 - i, \beta = 4 - 2i, \gamma = 2i$:

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i \\ 2 - i \\ 4 - 2i \\ 2i \end{pmatrix} \quad (126)$$

Here, $\lambda = \alpha/\beta = \frac{1}{2}, \theta_1 = \frac{1}{2} \arctan(\frac{1}{2}), \sin 2\theta_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}, \cos 2\theta_1 = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$. Hence, for a rotation by an angle θ_1 :

$$|h(\theta_1)\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i \\ 2 - i \\ 4 - 2i \\ 2i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i \\ 0 \\ \sqrt{5}(2 - i) \\ 2i \end{pmatrix} \quad (127)$$

For the rotated system $\alpha(\theta_1) = 0$, hence, only two output Stokes vectors will be enough to find the parameters associated with rotated the optical system. After finding the parameters of the rotated system it is possible to retrieve the parameters of the original system by the inverse rotation.

It is worth noting that, if α and β are pure real or pure imaginary the condition, $\alpha = \lambda\beta$, is automatically satisfied.

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